

The Kinetics of the Action of Ammonium Halides on Epichlorhydrin.

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A preliminary note on the action of alkali and ammonium halides on cyclohexene oxide was published by Sen and Barat (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 22) and subsequently, the kinetics of the action of epichlorhydrin and ethylene oxide were brought within the scope of investigation (*Proceedings of the Indian Science Congress*, 1927, p. 148). While the work was in progress, Brönsted, Kilpatric and Kilpatric published the kinetics of ethylene oxides (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 428) anticipating to a certain degree our results, although the experimental procedure and the motive were different in the two sets of investigations. Brönsted's object in studying this reaction was to provide a test for his theory of velocity of ionic reactions, according to which the velocity should be given by

$$h = k \cdot C_{OX} \cdot C_{H_3O}^+ \cdot C_{Cl}^- \cdot f^2$$

where C 's indicate the concentrations of the reacting molecules (the oxide being electrically neutral), and f , the activity coefficient of a univalent ion (*loc. cit.*). There is no doubt that this is a most generalised way of looking at chemical reactions, and the large mass of experimental data brought forward by these authors justify their point of view. We have, on the other hand, approached the interaction of ethylene oxides with salts from the classical orthodox point of view, and have discarded the hitherto believed basic nature of these oxides and have proved that the so-called basicity which was inferred from their power of precipitating oxides of certain metals, is only the result of their combination with the anion and the cation of the acid, the salt of which is brought into reaction. Indeed, the velocity of interaction between these oxides and the salts (haloids), is faster according as there is greater tendency for the formation of the particular halohydrin. Thus, the rates of reaction between chlorides, bromides and iodides with say, epichlorhydrin, are in the order iodide > bromide > chloride. Whilst Brönsted and

Kilpatrics (*loc. cit.*) maintain that 'the addition of acids exhibited by the ethylene oxides, is kinetically only to a minor extent the reason of their apparent basicity', we find, however, that the net result of the action of salt on these oxides, is *the addition of acid*, whatever may be the scheme of reaction. Now, the ability of a substance to add an acid is, by no means, a feature characteristic of bases. 'Bases are characterised by adding protons. Taking up the whole of an acid molecule, is something quite different from the basic function ; it depends upon the anion of the acid in an individual manner and need not have any relation to the strength of the acid added' (Brönsted and Kilpatrics, *loc. cit.*). In fact this is what we also have expressed in our preliminary notes when we have stated that potassium iodide is greater in reactivity than potassium bromide which again is greater in reactivity than potassium chloride with regard to these oxides.

Whether the interaction of acids leading to the addition to the oxides is fundamentally different from the action of their respective salts, is however not yet clear, because the mechanisms in the two reactions may not be the same. Thus, according to Brönsted, the addition of the acid through the salt and the addition of acid *per se* are represented by the two ionic equations :

This would evidently, so far as the velocity is concerned, involve according to reaction III, the individual characteristic of the anion, whereas in equation IV, the strength of the H-ion plays the important part. Hence, considered separately, the nature of the salt effect and the acid effect may not be the same. In fact, according to Brönsted although the strongest of all electrically neutral acids *viz.*, perchloric acid, does not react with ethylene oxides in the same way as do the hydro-halogen acids, yet in this group the addition velocity increases with the strength. In the following work, it is the salt effect of the ammonium halides that has been principally investigated. First, because the indicator method of titrating at a constant pH could only be correct for very low

concentrations of salts (in our case moderate to high concentrations have been used), and secondly, because whilst halogen salts of strong bases like potassium and sodium would give rise to strong bases capable of initiating the reverse reaction of reconverting the hydrins into oxides, ammonia is powerless to do so. In short, stating in Brønsted's terms, our investigations have been restricted to reaction III, with this distinction, however, that it is the three ammonium halides that have been investigated as regards their reactivity with these oxides. The usual method of following the salt effect in our case has been the estimation of ammonia generated with the lapse of time, the indicator used being at first methyl orange but later Wisslow's indicator (mixture of methyl red and methyl blue) and *N*/100-sulphuric acid.

It should be noted here that at such high concentrations of salts e.g., 0.4 mol per litre, the phenomenon of spontaneous glycolisation and that of its acceleration by H ion catalysis, though measurable, are not of much consequence, as approximately 90% conversion of the oxide into chlorhydrins, has been reached within a comparatively short period. Ammonia is the measure of the chlorhydrin produced and not of the glycolisation.

In conformity with the original object of this investigation, the action of yeast on these oxides in a fermenting sugar solution was also investigated, with the result that the presence of reaction II (*loc. cit.*)

i.e., glycolisation was confirmed, yeast being a hydrolytic enzyme. Thus, cyclohexene oxide when allowed to be in contact with a fermenting sugar solution gave cyclohexane-diol in practically quantitative yield, whilst the same with water gave the diol only at elevated temperatures, but that also in small quantities, indicating the comparatively small influence of reaction II in our experiments.

In order to ascertain whether the interaction of epichlorhydrin with ammonium halides is essentially different from the interaction of halogen acids with epichlorhydrin, experiments were performed with various strengths of hydrochloric acid, but in all cases the reaction was incomparably faster than the interaction of the ammonium halide. Thus 0.04*M* epichlorhydrin reacted with 1.2*M* ammonium chloride to the extent of 85% in 5 hours

whereas hydrochloric acid of similar strength (1.08M) reacted practically to completion in 5 minutes. A distinction however is noticed in the interaction of halogen acids (HCl investigated) with epichlorhydrin, where, with increased concentrations of acid, two molecules of HCl interact in the following way :

The addition of hydrochloric acid of different strengths on epichlorhydrin, was investigated quantitatively, not conductometrically but volumetrically in the following way: A solution of the oxide was mixed rapidly with a hydrochloric acid solution of known volume and known strength. After every 5 minutes or $\frac{1}{2}$ hour as the case may be, a known volume was pipetted off and treated with a weighed quantity of pure precipitated calcium carbonate of which the strength was previously ascertained from the stock bottle. After neutralisation of the remaining acid, the residual calcium carbonate was washed on a filter paper thoroughly, dissolved in a known amount of hydrochloric acid of known strength and the excess determined as usual. The difference between the acid equivalent of the total amount of carbonate taken and this later, gave the amount of hydrochloric acid in excess *not* added on to the oxide during the period considered. With a little practice, several experiments could be conducted in course of the working hours. This method has a decided advantage over Smith's method of estimating chlorhydrins (by heating with alkali and then titrating the ionically obtained chlorine with silver nitrate) for reason of its very simplicity; besides, treatment with alkali for several hours in a sealed flask at 70° is also obviated (Smith, Wode, Widhe, *Z. Phys Chem.*, 1927, 130, 154).

Addition of Hydrochloric Acid to Epichlorhydrin.

To 250 c.c. water 12.15 c.c. of HCl (d 1.19) were added. To 125 c.c. of this solution, an alcoholic solution of 0.4625 g. of epichlorhydrin was added and the whole kept at 36°. At intervals of 5 minutes the concentration of the acid was determined in the following way by withdrawing 10 c.c. portions of the reaction mixture.

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To 10 c.c. of the reaction mixture, 0.5 g. of CaCO_3 (the acid equivalent of which was previously determined) was added, the excess of the carbonate was then filtered off, washed thoroughly on the filter paper, and dissolved in a known excess of HCl of known strength, and the excess acid determined against $N\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3$ solution.

Volumetrically it was found previously that 10 c.c. of the acid solution contained 0.208 g. of HCl, (molarity of the acid = 0.57) 0.6 g. of CaCO_3 = 9.875 c.c. of $N\text{-HCl}$

After 5 minutes :

Residual CaCO_3 + 5 c.c. of 2N-HCl solution = 6.1 c.c. of $N\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3$; 5 c.c. of 2N-HCl = 10.8 c.c. of $N\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3$ solution.

\therefore Residual CaCO_3 = 10.8 - 6.1 = 4.7 c.c. of $N\text{-HCl}$ solution.

\therefore CaCO_3 used up by the acid present in 10 c.c. of the reaction mixture in 5 min. = 9.875 - 4.7 = 5.175 c.c. of $N\text{-HCl}$ = 0.1889 g. of HCl.

Acid originally present in 10 c.c. = 0.208 g.

\therefore Acid used up in 5 minutes by the epichlorhydrin present in 10 c.c. of the reaction mixture = 0.208 - 0.1889 = 0.0191 g.

\therefore Molarity of the acid used up = 0.052, molarity of epichlorhydrin = 0.04.

\therefore 1 Mol. of epichlorhydrin combines with 1.3 mol. of acid.

After 10 minutes :

Residual CaCO_3 + 5 c.c. of 2N-HCl solution = 6.1 c.c. of $N\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3$ solution *i.e.*, no change from the first reading.

After 15 minutes :

No change from the first reading.

Results of similar experiments with different concentrations of hydrochloric acid are given in the following table. The concentration of epichlorhydrin was 0.04M in each case.

TABLE I.		
Conc. HCl.	G. mols. of HCl used up.	No. of mols of HCl combining with 1 mol. of epichlorhydrin.
0.57 M	0.052	1.3
1.08 M	0.08	2.0
1.51 M	0.075	1.875
0.1 M	0.0135	0.335

Calculation of Velocity Constants.

As the temperature coefficients of these reactions were very large, care was taken to ensure the maintenance of the temperature of the thermostat within 0.005° and 0.01° . This was accomplished by electrical relays, and with a little care, it was found quite simple to secure such constancy for hours together without much attention. This was all the more necessary in order to exclude the difference in the values of velocity constants in the same set of experiments as arising from temperature variations. It must be stated in the very beginning that the calculation of the velocity constants presented serious difficulties, as these constants, whichever equation was taken as the basis for calculation, were not satisfactorily concordant. To take as an example, the velocity constants of the interaction between epichlorhydrin and ammonium chloride in molar concentrations of 0.04 and 0.4 respectively when calculated according to mono-molecular, a pseudo-monomolecular and a bimolecular equation, gave the following results.

TABLE II.

Time.	N/100- H ₂ SO used up.	$K = \frac{1}{t} \log a/a-x$		$K = \frac{1}{tb} \log a/a-x$	$K = \frac{1}{t(a-b)} \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$
		A	B		
1	hr. 2.915	0.0034	0.00125	0.00312	0.00313
2	4.890	0.0030	0.00108	0.0027	0.0030
3	7.019	0.0032	0.00106	3.00265	0.00269
4	8.817	0.0034	0.00103	0.00257	0.00261
5	10.709	0.0034	0.00103	0.00257	0.00263
24	15.797				

In B, C, and D, a stands for the molar concentration of the epichlorhydrin, and in A, a stands for the molar concentration corresponding to the total quantity of the epichlorhydrin actually used up at equilibrium, that is to say, if 0.04 molecule of epichlorhydrin is equivalent to x c.c. of N/100-H₂SO₄, and if at the end of the reaction, the total quantity of epichlorhydrin used up corresponds to y c.c. of sulphuric acid, under the column A, instead of using x c.c. as the active mass, 'y' the maximum titration value at equilibrium has been used. The use of this value of a has given

the most concordant values of velocity constants, calculated as a pure monomolecular reaction, which however is irreconcilable in view of the fact that the velocity constants vary with the concentration, and hence the reaction could by no means be considered a monomolecular one, but at best could be regarded as pseudo-monomolecular. The means of very closely agreeing constants are given in Table IV. There are, however, reasons to favour the adoption of the maximum titration figure as being the value of the initial active mass, *so far as this particular reaction is concerned*. Firstly, a sort of hydration of the oxide may remove a part of the epichlorhydrin from the sphere of direct reaction with the ammonium salt; secondly, other influences leading to hydration as indicated by reaction II, may be simultaneously acting, and as the rapidity of such hydroxylation in the presence of H ion is great, the active mass of epichlorhydrin actually available for reaction III, is naturally smaller than the initial molar quantity. One notices, however, that all these equations give a certain amount of agreement pointing to the bimolecular nature of the reaction involved, the variations being explained by the side reactions coming into force amongst which the salt effect is the most important.

One can view the whole scheme of reaction from a different point without materially affecting the explanation adduced above. This is based upon the hydrolysis of the ammonium salts in aqueous solution. The minute quantity of halogen acid which is generated thereby, is taken up by the oxide leading to further hydrolysis of the ammonium halide. In this way the concentration of free ammonia increases in the solution depending obviously on the velocity of ammonia liberation and the velocity of the halogen acid addition to the oxide itself. This explains the quicker evolution of ammonia with ammonium bromide and quickest in the case of ammonium iodide. Now, with the increase of ammonium ion in the solution, the hydrolysis of the ammonium halides will naturally be arrested after a time and probably this marks off the stage of equilibrium and maximum titration. With practically no hydrochloric acid in the solution, the conversion of ammonium chloride into ammonia may be regarded as a process of hydrolysis in the presence of a large excess of solvent, water. This way of regarding the scheme of reaction just lends a sort of support to the monomolecular values.

But a most generalised way of looking at the mechanism of the reaction would be not to regard it as arising out of the hydrolysis

of ammonium salts but of the H-ion condition of the solution. Thus a solution of potassium chloride which has an initial p_H 6.4, on treatment with epichlorhydrin, within a few minutes showed a p_H value. 9. In fact, if the p_H value be not allowed to reach the equilibrium value 9, by slowly neutralising the alkali as fast as it is formed, practically the whole of the potassium chloride could be decomposed corresponding to the epichlorhydrin present, and constants agreeing with the true bimolecular equation are obtained (cf. Brönsted, *loc. cit.*). In our titrations, no attempt was made in the beginning to keep the H-ion concentration constant, and hence no really concordant values for the constants fitting with the bimolecular equation could be obtained. The only constancy noticed under our experimental conditions was obtained by substituting our results to the following equation,

$$K = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{\xi}{\xi - x}$$

where ξ = equilibrium concentration of alkali; $\xi - x$ = the difference between equilibrium concentration and observed concentration of the alkali.

This feature of the reaction has been observed throughout the whole series of experiments (Table III) although no attention was paid to the maintenance of a constant p_H value of the reacting medium, the observance of which gave Brönsted and Kilpatrick's true bimolecular constants. It should be noted, however, that these investigators were working at considerably lower dilutions than in our case. Keeping a constant H-ion concentration in the ammonium halide solutions (these were not investigated by Brönsted), we obtained good bimolecular constants (Tables VI—IX). This would show that whatever may be the salt taken, a true bimolecular reaction takes place only when the p_H value of the particular reacting solution is kept constant. This is not antagonistic to the fact that different anions have different tendencies of addition on epichlorhydrin.

From a perusal of the values of the constants obtained below by using the maximum titration at equilibrium as the active mass of epichlorhydrin with varying molecular concentrations of ammonium halides, it is noticed that over a range of 2–5 (mol. conc. of ammonium halide, when the oxide is one) in the case of ammonium

chloride and bromide (Table IV), there is practically no change in the velocity constant. In the case of ammonium iodide, however, the change in the value of velocity constants is noticeable for every change in its concentration. With higher concentrations of any of these ammonium halides, there is a steady rise and there is irregularity in the value of the constants. But the velocity is considerably increased with the rise in the concentration (Table V). There is thus a positive salt effect. Constant p_a values were maintained by following Brönsted's experimental method (*loc. cit.* p. 441).

TABLE III.

Epichlorhydrin : NH_4Cl = 1 mol. : 1 mol. = .04 mol. : .04 Mol.

Time.	N/100- H_2SO_4 used up.	Value of 'K' with 'a' as maximum titration value at equilibrium.
1 hr.	0.409 c. c.	0.000656
2	0.727	0.000669
3	0.999	0.000682
4	1.182	0.000655
5	1.365	0.000658
6	1.59	0.00072
24	3.395	

TABLE IV.

Conc. epichlorhydrin = 0.04M			Temp. = 35°.			
Conc. NH_4Cl	...	0.08M	0.12M	0.16M	0.2M	
K	0.00295	0.0029	0.00294	0.0030
Conc. NH_4Br	...	0.04M	0.08M	0.12M	0.16M	0.2M
K	...	0.0227	0.0213	0.024	0.025	0.245
Conc. NH_4I	...	—	0.08M	0.12M	0.16M	
K	0.0442	0.0457	0.0496	

TABLE V.

Conc. NH_4Cl	...	0.4M	0.8M	1.2M	2M	
K	0.0038	0.00492	0.00556	0.00916
Conc. NH_4Br	0.4M	—	1.2M	2M
K	0.0174	—	0.033	0.0443
Conc. NH_4I	...	0.2M	0.4M	0.8M	—	2M
K	...	0.0658	0.0657	0.1147	—	0.2714

TABLE VI.

Epiclorhydrin : AmCl = 0.04 mol : 0.04 mol. Temp. 30°. $p_H = 4.6$.

Time in mins.	N/20-Perchloric acid taken up.	$K = \frac{1}{t} = \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$
8	0.091 c.c.	0.000355
13	0.113	0.000271
24	0.181	0.000235
28	0.203	0.000232
32	0.233	0.000227
37	0.261	0.000220
45	0.332	0.000230
49	0.356	0.000227
55	0.392	0.000223
58	0.415	0.000223
63	0.466	0.000231
67	0.482	0.000225
72	0.508	0.000220
77	0.550	0.000229

TABLE VII.

Epiclorhydrin : AmBr = 0.04 mol : 0.04 mol.

Time in mins.	N/10-Perchloric acid used up.	$K = \frac{1}{t} = \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$
11	0.28	0.00159
15	0.418	0.00174
21	0.476	0.00135
26	0.544	0.00130
31	0.640	0.00133
37	0.750	0.00128
40	0.812	0.00127
45	0.880	0.00122
51	1.037	0.00127
55	1.112	0.00126
60	1.170	0.00122
65	1.295	0.00125
70	1.352	0.00121

TABLE VIII.

Epiclorhydrin : AmBr = 0.04 mol : 0.16 mol. Temp. 31°. $p_H = 3.6$.

Time in mins.	N/10-Perchloric acid used up.	$K = \frac{1}{t(a-b)} \times \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$
6	0.575 c.c.	0.00127
13	1.265	0.00132
18	1.740	0.00128
25	2.306	0.00130
30	2.705	0.00134
36	3.520	0.00133
41	3.740	0.00136
46	4.390	0.00134
53	5.100	0.00137
62	5.580	0.00133
68	6.000	0.00132
72	6.322	0.00138
76	6.625	0.00134
80	6.854	0.00134

TABLE IX.

Epiclorhydrin : AmCl = 0.04 : 0.8 mol.

N/4-Perchloric acid used up.	$K = \frac{1}{t(a-b)} \times \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$	
14	0.72 c.c.	0.000867
21	1.00	0.000874
25	1.291	0.000863
28	1.410	0.000869
35	1.670	0.000871
39	1.875	0.000865
43	2.000	0.000866
47	2.182	0.000860
53	2.470	0.000865
57	2.645	0.000866
64	2.950	0.000864
68	3.100	0.000860
72	3.320	0.000861

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